

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D2.2: Website and project identity

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1 Project identity

1.1 Logo

Basic version of the logo

Inverse version of the logo

Protected area

1.2 Colour

1.3 Typography

Basic typography: Calibri, Calibri Light

Supporting typography: Cambria

1.4 Templates

1.4.1 Microsoft Word¹ – file: EURHISFIRM-WordTemplate-ver1.2

Margin: top 3.5 cm, bottom 3.0 cm, left 2.2 cm, right 2.2 cm

Basic typography: Calibri, 11 pts

Heading/Title 1 – Cambria, 14 pts, bold

Heading/Subtitle 2 – Cambria, 12 pts

Paragraph: justified, spacing 1.15, Calibri, 11 pts

EURHISFIRM aims at designing a world-class research infrastructure to collect, merge, extract, collate, align and share detailed historical high-quality firm level data for Europe. To achieve this goal, it develops innovative tools and sparks the “Big data” revolution in historical social sciences.

The EURHISFIRM project meets the need for such a benchmark research infrastructure in Europe. It will operate the most comprehensive long-run economic and financial database in the world. It will handle data on European companies such as accounting, funding and investment, stock exchange data, governance rules, directors, patents, location of headquarters. The creation of a vibrant European community will support the development of revolutionary RI technology, which in turn will enable a scientifically reproducible, technically sound and socio-legally robust evidence-base for the stakeholders. Not only policy makers and scholars will benefit from, but notably private companies: on the one hand, companies are major data users, the global spend for market data, an industry where US holds a quasi-monopoly, amounting to nearly 30 billion of dollars in 2015 (Burton and Taylor, 2016); on the other hand, the disruptive technologies developed within the RI will push further the technological frontier and bring major spin-offs to the European IT industry.

Bullets

- ▶ Sample – level 1
 - ▶▶ Sample – level 2
 - Sample – level 3

¹ This document was created using the EURHISFIRM template (WORD).

Table sample (Calibri, 10 pts)

	Name	Age	Sex	Profession
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

	Name	Age	Sex	Profession
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

1.4.2 Microsoft PowerPoint – file: EURHISFIRM-PowerpointTemplate-ver1.2

Layout – title slide

Layout – basic/content

Long-term data for Europe EURHISFIRM

<http://www.eurhisfirm.eu>

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 777489

Big data is a blanket term for the non-traditional strategies and technologies needed to gather, organize, process, and gather insights from large datasets. While the problem of working with data that exceeds the computing power or storage of a single computer is not new, the pervasiveness, scale, and value of this type of computing has greatly expanded in recent years.

Introduction

Layout – listing

Long-term data for Europe EURHISFIRM

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- ▶ **Goal 1:** To Finish On Time
- ▶ **Goal 2:** To Finish Under Budget
- ▶ **Goal 3:** To Meet The Requirements
- ▶ **Goal 4:** To Keep Customers Happy
- ▶ **Goal 5:** To Ensure A Happy Team

Goals of project

Layout – graph

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Sale of goods in UE

Sale of goods in the European Union, quarterly in 2023.

Quarter	Percentage
1. quarter	26%
2. quarter	25%
3. quarter	21%
4. quarter	28%

Sale of goods – graph

Layout – table

Long-term data for Europe **EURHISFIRM**

Country	1-6 Month	7-12 Month	Sum
Poland	345	234	579
France	566	456	1022
Germany	766	845	1611
Denmark	532	233	765
Italy	463	433	896

Table – example

Layout – final slide

Long-term data for Europe **EURHISFIRM**

What is Big Data?

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Thank you for your attention

2 Website

The project website is available on: www.eurhisfirm.eu.

